

Research Article

Sugarcane Squeeze: An Eco-Friendly Alternative to Plastic

Fatimah Sharini Mansor^{1,*}, Nur Izzatul Syahira Azman², Anis Sabrina Nadzri³, and Junaidah Hanim Ahmad⁴

¹ Faculty of Accountancy, University Technology MARA, Kelantan Branch; 2022601936@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0002-3430-8460

² Faculty of Accountancy, University Technology MARA, Kelantan Branch; 2022879446@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0006-6148-731X

³ Faculty of Accountancy, University Technology MARA, Kelantan Branch; 2022897966@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0007-3851-7055

⁴ Faculty of Accountancy, University Technology MARA, Kelantan Branch; jun_372@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0002-0502-797X

* Correspondence: 2022601936@student.uitm.edu.my; 019-9387607.

Abstract: *The excessive use of single-use plastics in Malaysia, particularly among outdoor enthusiasts, presents a significant challenge to achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12. Despite increased awareness, the convenience and low cost of plastic products contribute to severe environmental issues, including microplastic pollution. In response, Malaysia's "Roadmap Towards Zero Single-Use Plastics 2018-2030" aims to reduce plastic waste through comprehensive strategies involving all stakeholders. The SugarCane Squeeze offers a solution by replacing traditional plastics with a biodegradable squeeze bottle made from sugarcane bagasse. This innovative product is designed to be compact, durable, and eco-friendly, addressing both the practical needs of outdoor enthusiasts and the demand for sustainable alternatives. Its development represents a significant step towards reducing plastic waste and promoting environmental responsibility.*

Keywords: biodegradable, eco-friendly, plastic waste, sugarcane bagasse, sustainable alternatives.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13888398

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

The excessive use of plastics in Malaysia poses a significant challenge to achieve Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12, which emphasizes responsible consumption and production. Despite growing awareness of environmental issues, both manufacturers and consumers continue to prioritize convenience and cost over sustainability, often ignoring the long-term damage caused by plastic waste. This issue is particularly evident among outdoor enthusiasts such as hikers, campers, and adventurers who frequently rely on plastic products during their activities. The affordability and convenience of plastic gear and packaging encourage its widespread use, with little consideration for the environmental impact.

According to the Statista Research Department (2024), global plastic production reached a staggering 400.3 million metric tons in 2022, marking a 1.6 percent increase from the previous year. Moreover, plastic packaging waste is projected to rise from 142 million metric tons in 2019 to

approximately 380 million metric tons by 2060, which would account for nearly 40 percent of total plastic waste (Statista Research Department, 2024). In addition, based on a report published by the WORLD Wildlife Fund (WWF-Malaysia), Malaysia recorded an annual per capita plastic packaging per person is 16.8 in 2022. This has resulted Malaysia's position in the list of the top 10 countries to be main contributor to plastic pollution in the ocean. This growing problem emphasize a broader lack of awareness among consumers about how their overconsumption practices, including those related to outdoor activities contribute to environmental degradation and even harm individual well-being.

In response, Malaysia has introduced "The Roadmap Towards Zero Single-Use Plastics 2018-2030," a phased, evidence-based, and holistic approach to tackling single-use plastic pollution. This roadmap envisions a shift toward a more sustainable future by 2030, requiring the active participation of all stakeholders, including manufacturers and public, who play a crucial role in its success. To make this vision a reality, consumers must take proactive action to reduce and eventually eliminate their use of single-use plastics, even in the context of outdoor recreation.

While the government and other stakeholders will engage the public through Communication, Education, and Public Awareness (CEPA) initiatives to support this roadmap, the ultimate responsibility lies with each individual. Positive change depends on consumers adopting more responsible consumption and disposal habits, especially in activities like hiking and camping, rather than relying solely on government or non-governmental organizations' efforts. A collective shift in mindset and behaviour, particularly among outdoor enthusiasts, is essential to creating a cleaner, healthier environment for future generations.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

In recent years, it has become increasingly popular for young people to spend their free time engaging in activities like traveling, hiking, and camping. This demographic often favors the convenience of disposable items, particularly single-use plastics, during their adventures. However, this reliance on throwaway plastics significantly contributes to environmental pollution. For instance, plastic waste such as packaging, bottles, and wrappers frequently ends up as litter in natural settings. As these plastics degrade, they break down into microplastics, which contaminate soil and water sources, causing long-term damage to ecosystems.

To assess the impact of single-use plastic consumption among young outdoor enthusiasts, a multi-faceted approach was adopted. Data was collected through a survey conducted by The Harris Poll in August 2023, targeting over 1,000 U.S. adults who regularly engage in outdoor activities such as hiking, biking, yoga, and camping. The survey revealed that more than two out of every five outdoor enthusiasts (43%) admitted to using single-use plastic water bottles during these activities. Additionally, 89 percent of respondents acknowledged having used single-use plastic water bottles in the last month, with 48 percent reporting the use of 10 or more bottles within that time frame.

This survey data was supplemented with field observations and environmental impact assessments. These assessments focused on the prevalence of plastic waste, including water bottles, packaging, and wrappers, found in natural environments frequented by outdoor enthusiasts. The study monitored the degradation process of these plastics, particularly how they break down into microplastics that contaminate soil and water sources. This method provides a comprehensive understanding of the consumption patterns of single-use plastics in outdoor activities and the resulting environmental implications.

3. FINDINGS

The research highlights a critical need for alternatives to single-use plastics, especially among outdoor enthusiasts who prioritize convenience in their activities. The study identified a strong demand for products that can match or surpass plastics in functionality, durability, and convenience, without compromising environmental sustainability. To address this need, the introduction of the SugarCane Squeeze bottle represents a promising solution.

The SugarCane Squeeze bottle is designed as a compact, convenient, and eco-friendly alternative to traditional plastic containers, specifically targeting travellers, hikers, and campers who often face the challenge of limited packing space. Its small size eliminates the necessity for multiple separate items, offering a streamlined and efficient option for those on the move.

The use of sugarcane as the primary material not only supports the growing demand for sustainable products but also appeals to eco-conscious consumers by significantly reducing reliance on traditional plastics. The biodegradable nature of the packaging underscores the product's alignment with environmental goals, making it an attractive option for consumers seeking to minimize their ecological footprint.

By addressing both practical needs and environmental concerns, the SugarCane Squeeze bottle successfully fills a gap in the market. It provides a versatile, durable, and eco-friendly alternative that promotes a sustainable lifestyle among outdoor enthusiasts and frequent travellers. The findings suggest that this product has the potential to drive significant positive change in consumer behaviour, reducing the impact of plastic waste on natural environments while meeting the demands of modern, on-the-go lifestyles.

4. DISCUSSION

The SugarCane Squeeze represents a forward-thinking solution designed to address two critical concerns: easing the burden on outdoor enthusiasts and protecting the environment. This innovative product is a compact, biodegradable squeeze bottle crafted from sugarcane bagasse; a byproduct often discarded as waste. By repurposing this material into a high-value resource, the SugarCane Squeeze offers a practical and eco-friendly alternative to traditional plastic containers, particularly for those who engage in outdoor activities.

The design of the SugarCane Squeeze is tailored to meet the specific needs of travellers, hikers, and campers who require efficient packing solutions. Its small size allows for easy storage in any backpack, ensuring that users can carry essential items without taking up excessive space. The bottle's unique tip design further enhances its practicality by enabling easy application of sauces and other contents without the need for additional cutlery, adding to its convenience as a space-saving tool.

What truly sets the SugarCane Squeeze apart is its sustainable material and manufacturing process. By utilizing sugarcane bagasse, a renewable resource, and converting it into plant-based plastic through fermentation, the product embodies a commitment to environmental responsibility. The resulting material is not only biodegradable but also lightweight, durable, and dishwasher-safe, making it a viable alternative to traditional fossil fuel-derived plastics.

This approach not only addresses the environmental impact of plastic waste but also aligns with the growing consumer demand for sustainable products. By offering a biodegradable option that doesn't compromise on durability or convenience, the SugarCane Squeeze positions itself as a novel and sustainable alternative in a market that is increasingly shifting towards eco-friendly solutions.

Sustainability is the cornerstone of this business. Every aspect of the SugarCane Squeeze, from its eco-friendly ingredients to its biodegradable nature, reflects a commitment to reducing environmental impact. The innovative use of renewable resources in its production process demonstrates that it is possible to create practical, high-quality products that also contribute to a healthier planet.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, SugarCane Squeeze is more than just a product. It is a solution to real problems faced by outdoor enthusiasts, and a response to the global need for sustainable alternatives. The researchers have developed this product with a deep understanding of the market, the challenges that target customers face, and the broader environmental impact. The research team has leveraged cutting-edge innovation to create something that is not only useful and practical but also contributes to a better future. Thus, the researchers are confident that SugarCane Squeeze will not only meet the needs of consumers but will also play a role in driving the market towards more sustainable practices.

Acknowledgments: We would like to extend our deepest gratitude to Faculty of Business & Management UiTM Cawangan Kelantan and Malaysia Academy of SME & Entrepreneurship Development UiTM Cawangan Kelantan for organizing and providing us opportunity to join 3 Minute Business Idea Pitch & Innovation Competition 2024 (3MPIC). A special thanks to our advisor Madam Junaidah Hanim Ahmad for the endless support and contributions during this competition. To our dedicated team, thank you for your hard work and determination. Lastly, we are immensely grateful for giving us opportunity to introduce our business idea which is SugarCane Squeeze which our aim is to achieve sustainability for the future

References

- Mahmud, M. A., Belal, S. A., & Gafur, M. A. (2023). Development of a biocomposite material using sugarcane bagasse and modified starch for packaging purposes. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, 24, 1856–1874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2023.03.083>
- Malaysia's Roadmap towards Zero Single-Use Plastics, 2018 – 2030 – Malaysian Green Technology And Climate Change Corporation. (n.d.). <https://www.mgtc.gov.my/plastic/>
- Reporter, S. (2023, April 26). Biodegradable and sustainable packaging alternatives to drive the sugarcane packaging. *Farmers Review Africa*. <https://farmersreviewafrica.com/biodegradable-and-sustainable-packaging-alternatives-to-drive-the-sugarcane-packaging-market-to-us-889-0-million-by-2033/>
- THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development. (n.d.). <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- WWF releases report proposing effective solution to mitigate plastic P. (n.d.). <https://www.wwf.org.my/?28105/WWF-Releases-Report-Proposing-Effective-Solution-to-Mitigate-Plastic-Pollution-in-Malaysia>